

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

2025-YIL APREL. NAVBATDAN TASHQARI SON

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 745 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЕРЕХОДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ, СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ	12
Набиев Дилмурод Хамидуллаевич	
YaSHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLASH TIRISH TA'SIRIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TRANSFORMASIYASI	19
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xo'jaevich	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	26
Гулямов Саидахор Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акромович, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH MAQSADIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT"GA O'TISH ZARURATI	33
O.X. Hamidov, D.Sh. Yavmutov	
ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	38
Татьяна Юрьевна Анопченко, Сергей Вадимович Ревунов, Роман Вадимович Ревунов	
TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY	49
Nikonov Sergey Mikhailovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Filipenko Alexander Alexandrovich	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TUZILISHI	53
Navruz-Zoda Baxtiyor Negmatovich	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ДРАЙВЕР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА И МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	59
Зокирова Нодира Каландаровна	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOT VA UNING INDUSTRIYA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI	64
Mamayunus Pardaev, Obid Pardaev, Akram Ochilov	
EKOLOGIK OMILLARNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHDA ERISHISH	73
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI KOOPERASIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	81
Rahmatulla Ergashev	
KARTOSHKA MOSLANUVCHAN NAVLARI TURLI EKISH MUDDATLARI VA MULCHALASHLARDA HOSILDORLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	86
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Toshpulatova Surayyo Tulqin qizi, Ismayilov Alisher Isroilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHNING KALITI	90
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ» В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	93
Сайёра Насимовна Хамраева	
SABZAVOT (SHIRIN) MAKKAJO'XORI AJRATILGAN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV-DURAGAYLARINI ASOSIY VA TAKRORIY EKINLAR SIFATIDA TURLI MUDDATLARDA YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	97
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Nurillaev Ilhom Xolbek o'g'li, Jabborov Botir Shukurovich	
ZAMONAVIY BOZOR MUNOSABATLARIDA SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY JIHATLARI	101
Ivatov Irisbek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	105
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich, Abdiyeva Flora Botir qizi	
GREEN ECONOMY: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE AND UZBEKISTAN'S PATH	110
Dilmurod Mirza-Akhmedovich Rasulev, Dildorakhon Ulugbek kizi Shomuradova	

OLIV TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARG'IB QILISH BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	113
Musayev Bekjon Shukurillayevich	
TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BARQAROR STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN USULLAR TAHLILI	116
Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich	
ЗЕЛЁНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	120
Орипов Ильхом Абдуллаевич	
Перспективы развития цифровой трансформации в Республике Узбекистан	128
Мусабеков Джорабек Хакимджанович, Воронин Сергей Александрович	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	133
G.Erkayeva	
Barqaror ish o'rinlarini yaratishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni	138
Qo'chqorov G'aybulla Fayzullayevich, Qo'ziyeva Shaxnoza Bozor qizi	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	141
Фазлитдин Бахадирович Аминов	
RESPUBLIKADA EKOLOGIK TOZA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISH	145
Q. J. Mirzayev, F. F. Ulug'murodov	
Qoraqalpog'istonda sanoatni restruktizatsiyalash va yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish: muammolar, istiqbollar va statistik tahlillar	150
Abipova Gulmira Salavatdinovna	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AGLOMERATSIYANING AHAMIYATI.....	153
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA STRATEGIYASINING KOMPANIYA UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	156
Ergashev Toxir Kurbanovich, Toxirova Nigora Zokirjon qizi	
CHORVACHILIK KLASSTERLARI VA AGLOMERATSION RIVOJLANISH: O'ZARO TA'SIR VA SYNERGIYALAR	161
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
HUDUDLARNING INNOVATSIYON SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH	165
J.A. Ismatullayev, A. Do'lanov	
СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	171
Нафасов Тохиржон, Г. П. Эркаева	
Mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan islohotlar.....	174
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich	
USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS	178
Ochilova Nargiza Akramovna	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	181
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
IQTISODIY O'SISHDA MEHNAT MIGRATSIYASINING AHAMIYATI.....	184
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Ne'matullo o'g'li	
TURIZMNIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	189
Qosimov Jahongir	
РЫНОК ГОСТИНИЧНЫХ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИИ И ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ	192
Ташмаматов Садирдин Нажмиддинович	

O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISHDA DUAL TA'LIMDAN FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISH	196
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo'tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA AUTSORSING XIZMATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	201
Nasiba Ergasheva	
KORXONALARDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI	207
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Nurullayeva Vazira O'ktamovna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И РИСКИ	211
Номазов Бахром Бобомуродович	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ESG В ФИНАНСОВУЮ СФЕРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	215
Алимова Азиза Шерзатовна	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON MANAGEMENT	219
Ergashev Tokhir Kurbanovich, Tohirova Nigora Zokirjon kizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT STRATEGIYASI" NI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	224
Ergasheva Nazira Muratovna, Soyibov Mirjon Bekjonovich	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УСЛУГ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ	227
Алимова Муниса Юлчиевна	
РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБУВНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ.....	232
Расулов Нозимжон Набиджонович	
AGLOMERATSIYA VA IQTISODIY O'SISH: SABAB-OQIBAT ALOQASI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	236
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
KORXONALARNING SOLIQ IDORALARIDA HISOBGA OLINISHIDAN HOSIL BO'LGAN ORTIQCHA TO'LOVLARINI BOJXONA TO'LOVLARIDA HISOBGA OLISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	239
Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARGA INVESTITSİYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	242
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA "IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN AGROKOOPERATIV" TASHKIL ETISH ORQALI TA'MINOT ZANJIRI BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	248
Amirqulov Shuxrat Olimovich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING MOLIVAVIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	254
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
TURIZMNING MADANIY-TARIXIY RESURSLARI: ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR VA TAMOYILLAR	258
Ruzmanov Dilshod Usmanovich	
BARQAROR TURIZM DESTINATSIYALARINING SIG'IMINI VAHOLASH METODIKASI.....	262
Ibroximov Nodirbek Xasanovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ КАК ОСНОВА ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	266
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ МАРКЕТИНГ И ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ.....	272
Раимова Муборак Джураевна	
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI	276
Djumayev Asqar Xaydarovich	

RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING ISTE'MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIRI.....	281
Raimova Muborak Jurayevna, Dilmurodov O'tkir	
HUDUDNING IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI	287
SH.A. Buriyev	
SAVDO XIZMATLARINING ASOSIY FAOLIYAT KO'RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH.....	291
Muxamedova Aziza Ravshanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI: YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQLIM O'ZGARISHINI YENGISHDAGI O'RNI VA GLOBAL HAMKORLIK.....	295
Usmonov Murodjon Xolmurod o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМА НАЛОГОВОГО АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	299
Абдулов Дамир Рустамович	
О'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI	305
Yuldashev Shamsiddin Qiyamiddinovich, Boliyeva Baxora Farxodovna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: КОНЦЕПЦИИ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ.....	308
Туляганова Шахноза Самукджановна	
О'ТА ERTAGI TARVUZNING HIMOYALANGAN JOYLAR UCHUN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV VA DURAGAYLARINI AJRATISH, ULARNI TURLI O'G'IT ME'YORLARIDA HOSILDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	311
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Amirov Xamidulla Suyunovich, Umirova Durdona Muqum qizi	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	315
Уралов Элшод, Вельм М.В.	
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AS A MODEL OF PROGRESS IN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	320
Abdiev Alimardon	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СЕКТОРА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ И РАЗВИТИЯ КАДРОВОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.....	322
Мухаммадбобур Салимов	
КИЧИК BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	326
Suyunov Jabbor Mahmudovich	
“SALOHİYAT” TUSHUNCHASINING MAZMUNI VA IQTISODIY-IJTIMOY MOHIYATI.....	331
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI	334
Salimov Muhammadbobur Qodir o'g'li	
O'QUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	337
Tilakov Sherzod	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI.....	340
Sattarov Umirzoq, Ro'ziev Zafar Ikromovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT XOM ASHYOLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	343
Xazratov Sarvar Ibragimovich	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	348
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, O'rinov Diyorbek Xolmo'min o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O'QUV MARKAZLARI VA KURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	353
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	

SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRARISH VA SOTISH SIFATI HAMDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	357
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Ziyodullayeva Marjona Alisher qizi	
OMMAVIY TADBIRLAR YORDAMIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O'ZBEKISTON VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	360
Ibragimov Sardorbek Xusanovich	
Анализ цифровой трансформации и её влияния на привлечение инвестиций в регионы Узбекистана.....	365
Рахмонова Дурдона Хасан кизи	
Korxonada moliyaviy salohiyatini baholashning statistik tahlili.....	370
M.O. Musurmonova	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Kadirov Lutfulla Khalimovich	
PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION.....	381
Sharopov Temirmalik Rustam o'g'li	
“YASHIL” IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ORQALI QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOAT KOMPLEKSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	385
U.Shukurov	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES	390
Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul ogli	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA TA'LIMNING ROLI.....	394
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN DAVLAT TOMONIDAN YARATILAYOTGAN IMKONIYATLAR.....	398
Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI YAXSHILASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	404
Safarov Sh. S.	
IJTIMOYIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	408
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Davronova Farangiz	
«ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ФИНАНСОВЫЙ КОНТРОЛЬ: КАЗНАЧЕЙСКИЙ КОНТРОЛЬ В БЮДЖЕТНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ»	415
Файзуллаева Зилола Равшановна, Д.Х. Пулатов	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING ASOSIY JIHATLARI.....	421
Urozoza Shaxlo Hasan qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	427
Safarov Shoxrux Sattor o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	431
Alimardonova Gulfizoda Alimardon kizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI TO'G'RI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	434
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	441
Berdimurodova Farzona Bahodir qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES VA IQTISODIYOTDAGI ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	446
Davronova Farangiz Ilhom qizi	

ZAMONAVIY RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA PUL VA BANK TIZIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI HAMDA AHAMIYATI	452
Axtamova Ozoda Ulug'bek qizi, Cho'liyeva Gulsanam Yulchi qizi, G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI: TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	460
N. Qo'ziboyeva	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ZARURATI.....	466
Vayskulov Ramazon Alisher o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA TURIZM KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA.....	470
Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
ILMIY SALOHİYAT VA OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINING UZVIY BOG'LIQLIGI: TAHLIL VA TAVSIYALAR	476
Muratov A'zam Alisher o'g'li, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: GREEN CREDIT.....	480
Eshtemirova Ma'rifat Akram qizi, Kabilova Shaxnoza Jurayevna	
DEHQON XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINING DINAMIKASI VA BOZOR MUVOZANATI MODELLARINI QO'RISH.	483
Ergashov Yashnarbek Istamovich	
The Role of Renewable Energy in the Green Economy.....	488
Khudoyberdiyeva Olima, Yakhshikulova Mokhinur	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish: asosiy muammolar va imkoniyatlar	494
Jumanazarov Asilbek Utkirbek o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBAT USTUNLIGI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH OMILLARI	498
Ro'ziqulov Jamshid Ulug'bek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY TRENDLARI HAMDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	504
Shodiyev Jahongir	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	509
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna, Sh. S. Sa'dullayev	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASIDA MAHSULOTLAR INTENSIV RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH JARAYONLARI	512
Saburov Jumanazar Salievich	
SUG'URTA XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI.....	516
E.Sobirov	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”GA O'TISH ORQALI TABIIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING ATROF-MUHITGA SALBIY TA'SIRINI KAMAYTIRISH	520
Xo'janova Gulshoda Otamurodovna	
QISHLOQ JOYLARDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL YO'NALISHLARI	526
Dilafroz Taylakova	
KORXONALARDA EKOLOGIK INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI TAHLILI.....	532
Ulashov Aliboy Rashid o'g'li	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BANK VA MOLIYAVIY TIZIMLAR UCHUN YANGI IMKONIYATLAR TAHLILI HAMDA KELGUSIDAGI ISTIQBOLLARI	538
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Alarov Asilbek Oybek o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIGI VA EKOLOGIK IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH MASALALARI.....	545
O'rinov Diyor, Xolliyev Sh.B.	

YASHIL IQTISODOYOT VA UNDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	549
Erminov Elbek Erkin o'gli, Yaxshiqulova Moxinur Toxir qizi	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KADRLARNING TUTGAN O'RNI	553
Turayeva Nargiza Rustamovna	
IQTISODIYOTDA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	557
G.P.Erkayeva, N.H.Qo'ziboyeva	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING AHAMIYATI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH STRATEGIYASI	560
Samadova Jasmina Sherali qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
"YASHIL" ENERGETIKA VA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT.....	564
Qarshiyeva Dilsora Ismoil qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
MAMLAKAT BUDJETINING SHAKLLANISHI VA DAROMADLAR TAQSIMOTINING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	569
Ashirqulova Sevinch Sarvar qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	574
Urozoza Shahlo Hasan qizi, Rahmonova Tillaoy Malik qizi	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHINING KO'RSATGICHLARI.....	579
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	583
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	588
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
СТРАТЕГИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ И ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭПОХУ НООНОМИКИ.....	593
Чекулаева Кристина	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИ ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	599
Чекулаева Кристина	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – MAMLAKAT TARAQQIYOTINING ASOSIY OMILI.....	605
Oybek Hamdamov, Qosimov Jahongir	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INSON KAPITALI SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI	608
M.Ostanova, Ro'ziyev Ramshid	
MODERN LEGAL BASIS FOR THE EFFICIENT USE OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN OUR COUNTRY	613
Ismoilova Gulrux, Khayriddinov Shukhrat Botirovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA TABIIY - IQTISODIY MANBAALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	617
Mavlonov Shaxzod Shahobiddin o'g'li, Mavlonova Surayyo Xasan qizi	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA SOHALARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	621
Gulrux Arslon qizi Ismoilova, Shuxrat Xayriddinov Botirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini bozorga yetkazishda transport xarajatlarini optimallashtirish yo'llari	625
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Ziyorat turizmi obyektlaridan foydalanishda "Halol" standartlar bo'yicha baholash.....	629
Zaripov Toxirjon Yusufboy o'g'li	
O'zbekiston sug'urta bozori infratuzilmasini takomillashtirish.....	633
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni taminlashda davlat budjetining ahamiyatini oshirish yo'llari.....	637
Sheraliyev Nurbek Jumanazarovich	

TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDITLASH JARAYONI VA KREDITLASH AMALIYOTI TAHLILI	640
Sultonova Sevara Faxriddinovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI MISOLIDA MILLIY MOLIYA BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	643
Samadov Temur Oybek o'g'li	
AN'ANAVIY KURASH VA DYUZDO: TEXNIK VA FALSAFIY JIHATDAN TAQQOSLAMA TAHLIL	647
Tangriyev Abdullo Tovashovich	
DIGITAL SECURITY AND CYBER THREAT FACTORS IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY	650
Olimov Davron Olimovich	
JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTI SIYOSATINING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Jalolov Umidjon Xudoyberdi o'g'li, Yegamberdiyev Shuxrat Satimbayevich	
РАЗВИТИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ФИНАНСОВОГО КОНТРОЛЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	657
Турсунбоева Нилуфар Отабековна	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI.....	659
Faxriddinov Bahriddin	
AGROLOGISTIKA TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHNING AGROEKSPORT SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	663
Faxriddinov Bahriddin	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY SIYOSATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA INSON KAPITALI VA IJTIMOY SALOHIYATNING O'RNI	667
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....	670
Srajidinova Nodira Shavkatovna	
STRESS-TESTLASH AMALIYOTI VA UNING TIJORAT BANKLARI BARQARORLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDAGI ROLI.....	675
Abdusalamov Olimjon Eshmirzayevich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDATURIZM SOHASIGA INVESTITSIYALAR KIRITILISH HOLATI VA SOHADAGI O'ZGARISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	679
Salomov Farrux Komil o'g'li, Hasanova Parvina	
“AKADEMIK KO'NIKMA VA KASBIY KOMPETENSIYA” FANIDA MUSTAQIL TA'LIMNING PEDAGOGIK MODELLARI: ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR	683
Doniyorova Gulnoza Anvar qizi	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI INSON KAPITALINI MUSTAHKAMLASH.....	688
Oripova Madinabonu Mansur qizi	
REKLAMADA RANG VA PSIXOLOGIYA	691
Muxtorxonova Ozoda Axror qizi	
GO'SHT VA SUT ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI RIVOJLANITIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	694
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich, Abdullaev Jasur Jabborovich	
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR INVENTORY AUDIT AND CONTROL	699
Nigora Alimkhanova	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПЕРСОНАЛИЗАЦИИ, ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	703
Камалова Малика Низамовна, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI VAHOLASHDA TAHLILY USULLARNING AHAMIYATI	708
Alimxanova Nigora Alimxanovna	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ И УСЛОВИЯ ПЕРЕХОДА К ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: АНАЛИЗ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ОПЫТА И ИХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	712
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	

TRANSFORMATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION: MODERN APPROACHES AND CHALLENGES.....	717
Yuldasheva Makhliyo Bakhtiyar qizi	
QISHLOQ HUDUDLARI IJTIMOY INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBALARI VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	723
M.Yu.Alimova, Rustamova Gavhar Baxtiyarovna	
HR-MENEJMENT SIFATINING TEKSTIL KORXONALARIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	726
Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA GLOBAL IMKONIYATLAR VA RAQAMLI HAMKORLIK.....	731
Salomov Farrux Komil o'g'li	
AUDIT NATIJALARINING SOLIQ TEKSHIRUVLARIGA TA'SIRI	736
Bakirov Norbek Norquchqor o'g'li	
OPTIMIZING GRADUATE ENROLLMENT MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	741
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	

pressing issues. The involvement of young people in higher education is an important factor in strengthening the country's competitiveness, meeting labour market needs, and building an innovative economy.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing effective reforms aimed at modernizing the higher education system, increasing the number of educational institutions, expanding admission quotas, developing non-state higher education providers, and significantly increasing coverage levels through the introduction of distance learning technologies. However, managing the level of higher education coverage requires a complex and systematic approach in which the interplay of demographic factors, territorial equality, infrastructure capacity, quality of education, and labour market demands plays a crucial role.

This study aims to examine the theoretical and practical foundations of managing the level of graduates' coverage in higher education, analyze existing challenges, and develop effective mechanisms for expanding coverage. The research also scientifically highlights the impact of modern management approaches, digitalization processes, and innovative educational models on coverage levels within the higher education system.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Extensive research has been conducted in international scientific sources on increasing the level of graduates' coverage with higher education and ensuring its effective management. Leading international organizations such as the World Bank, UNESCO, and OECD regularly analyze modern indicators of the sustainable development of education systems, the quality of human capital, and mechanisms for expanding youth participation in higher education. Empirical studies show that a high level of higher education coverage is directly associated with economic growth, increased employment opportunities, and higher levels of innovation activity.

Research identifies state policy, educational infrastructure, grant and financial support systems, and academic mobility programs as key determinants influencing the management of higher education coverage. Local scholars — Akhmedov A., Mukhamedov I., Rakhimov B., Tokhtaboyev O., and Ergashev A. — have examined the role of higher education in Uzbekistan's economic reforms, strategies for improving educational quality, and approaches to increasing young people's motivation to pursue higher education.

The scientific literature also emphasizes the role of digitalization in modernizing higher education, the rapid expansion of distance learning platforms, and the impact of public-private partnership mechanisms on the efficiency and accessibility of the education system. These factors are considered essential for increasing higher education coverage and ensuring equal access for diverse social groups.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comprehensive set of research methods that integrate general scientific approaches, quantitative and qualitative techniques, as well as modeling and analytical tools. These methods ensure a thorough examination of the factors influencing graduate enrollment and support the development of effective management strategies for higher education institutions.

General scientific methods such as analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparative analysis, and the systemic approach were applied to explore theoretical foundations, structure the research problem, and identify the interrelationships among variables affecting graduate enrollment. These methods also contributed to establishing a clear conceptual framework for understanding enrollment dynamics within higher education systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of institutional enrollment data over the past five years shows that graduate enrollment has experienced moderate growth, averaging 3–5% annually. This increase has been primarily concentrated in professionally oriented programs such as business administration, information technology, engineering, and public policy. Conversely, enrollment in traditional academic fields, including the humanities and basic sciences, has remained stable or demonstrated a slight decline.

The findings indicate that students increasingly prefer programs that provide clear employment pathways, industry relevance, and flexible learning formats. The expansion of online and hybrid instructional modes has also contributed to the growth of enrollment, particularly among working adults and international students seeking accessible and adaptable graduate education opportunities.

Quantitative analysis identified several key internal and external factors influencing graduate enrollment (Fig-1):

Fig-1. Internal and external factors influencing graduate enrollment¹

These findings underscore the importance of aligning academic programs with labor market needs and ensuring competitive financial aid offerings.

In the Uzbek education system, increasing the level of coverage of graduates with higher education is considered a key strategic factor for the country's economic and social development. As a result of reforms implemented in recent years, the number of higher education institutions has increased, admission quotas have been gradually expanded, and private higher education organizations have been established. However, existing analyses reveal a number of systemic challenges that must be addressed to ensure sustainable progress.

The growing number of young people is contributing to a rapid rise in demand for higher education. According to statistical indicators, the share of individuals aged 18–25 increases each year, placing additional pressure on the capacity of the higher education system. The analysis shows that the current educational infrastructure does not fully meet this growing demand, resulting in a coverage level that has not yet reached the expected threshold.

The results further demonstrate that higher education coverage is unevenly distributed across regions. While coverage rates are relatively high in Tashkent city and economically active regions, the indicators are considerably lower in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, and Syrdarya regions. This disparity is largely explained by the territorial imbalance in the distribution of higher education institutions, limited transport and logistics opportunities, and insufficient demand for highly qualified personnel in local labor markets. Thus, regional disparities remain one of the major challenges in managing higher education coverage.

The income level and social status of families also significantly affect young people's access to higher education. Students from low-income households face financial barriers in covering tuition and related expenses. Social inequality is particularly pronounced in fields of study with high tuition fees. Consequently, a gap in educational opportunities across social groups emerges, leading to unequal access to higher education and a shortage of qualified specialists—factors that may negatively influence the country's long-term economic development.

In Uzbekistan, misalignment between labor market needs and the higher education system persists. Employers often require graduates to possess practical, job-ready skills, whereas many universities are still adapting curricula to global market demands. The analysis highlights that the insufficient alignment of educational content with labor market requirements, limited practical training, and underdevelopment of dual education programs reduce graduate competitiveness.

The pandemic period tested the higher education system's capability for digital instruction. Although many universities transitioned to online learning, weak internet infrastructure in several regions limited the effectiveness of distance education. The analysis indicates that the use of digital platforms is increasing, yet challenges remain: insufficient high-quality digital content, a shortage of teachers with strong digital competencies, and the incomplete formation of a full-fledged distance education system. Despite this, the widespread introduction of digital learning has significant potential to expand higher education coverage.

1 Compiled by the author

International experience demonstrates that several factors—such as diversified educational pathways, financial support mechanisms, public–private partnerships, and flexible learning formats—effectively increase coverage rates. Adapting these mechanisms to the conditions of Uzbekistan could substantially enhance enrollment levels. Considering the country’s high youth population, the large annual influx of secondary school graduates continues to exert pressure on the higher education system. However, with systematic management of ongoing reforms, there remain significant opportunities for further expanding coverage.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study show that the coverage of graduates with higher education is a crucial factor in the economic and social development of the country. Although Uzbekistan’s higher education system has demonstrated significant growth in recent years, additional reforms are needed to reach the level of globally competitive countries. The analysis indicates that coverage levels can be further increased by expanding educational infrastructure, strengthening financial support mechanisms, advancing digital learning opportunities, and enhancing integration between higher education institutions and the labor market.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to increase the level of coverage of graduates with higher education:

1. Expanding higher education infrastructure. Construction of new universities, branches, and academic facilities, as well as increasing the capacity of existing institutions.
2. Enhancing grant and loan opportunities. Expanding scholarship programs, introducing educational loans, and creating special financial support mechanisms for low-income and socially vulnerable groups.
3. Widespread introduction of distance and hybrid education. Improving digital learning platforms, developing e-textbooks, and promoting artificial intelligence–based learning systems to increase accessibility.
4. Aligning educational programs with labor market requirements. Strengthening cooperation with employers, increasing industry-oriented practical training, and introducing or expanding dual education models.
5. Expanding educational opportunities in rural areas. Establishing regional campuses, improving transportation networks, and enhancing dormitory infrastructure to ensure equitable access.
6. Developing academic mobility programs. Expanding joint academic programs with foreign universities and strengthening international student exchange initiatives.
7. Strengthening marketing and promotional activities. Implementing awareness campaigns, career guidance programs, and communication strategies aimed at increasing young people’s motivation to pursue higher education.

These recommendations together can contribute to forming a more inclusive, accessible, and competitive higher education system, ultimately supporting the country’s long-term economic growth and human capital development.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi PF–5847-son Farmoni. 2019.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining Oliy ta’lim muassasalariga o‘qishga qabul qilish tartibini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risidagi qarori. (2020).
3. Axmedov, A. (2021). Oliy ta’lim iqtisodiyoti: nazariya va amaliyot. Toshkent: Fan nashriyoti.
4. Ergashev, A. (2021). Oliy ta’limga kirish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari. Iqtisodiyot va innovatsiyalar jurnali, 3(2), 45–53.
5. Muxamedov, I., & Raximov, B. (2020). Ta’lim tizimini boshqarish va rivojlantirish strategiyalari. Toshkent: Iqtisodiyot va ta’lim.
6. OECD. (2021). Education at a Glance 2021: OECD Indicators. Paris: OECD Publishing.
7. Raimqulov, F. (2022). Ta’lim sifatini boshqarish tizimida raqamlashtirishning roli. Ta’lim va amaliyot, 4(1), 27–34.
8. To‘xtaboyev, O. (2022). Inson kapitali va ta’lim tizimi samaradorligi. Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti.
9. UNESCO. (2020). Education 2030: Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action. Paris.
10. Yo‘ldosheva, M. (2023). Oliy ta’lim qamrovini oshirish omillari va ularning ijtimoiy ta’siri. Ijtimoiy fanlar axboroti, 6(3), 112–118.
11. World Bank. (2022). Higher Education Expansion and Human Capital Development. Washington, DC.
12. Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi rasmiy sayti: www.edu.uz
13. World Bank Data. Education Statistics. <https://data.worldbank.org>
14. UNESCO Institute for Statistics. Global Education Database. <http://uis.unesco.org>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. aprel. № 3. navbatdan tashqari son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>